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Original article

ROLE OF HEART RATE RESPONSE TO STANDING AND VALSALVA MANOEUVRE MEASUREMENT IN DIAGNOSING CARDIOVASCULAR AUTONOMIC NEUROPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Diabetes is an iceberg disease with many complications like cardiovascular disease & diabetic neuropathy. One of the most overlooked of all serious complications of diabetes is cardiovascular autonomic neuropathy (CAN), Autonomic nervous system dysfunction is one of the significant complications of diabetes mellitus and this is generally associated with a poor prognosis. Standard cardiovascular reflex tests are used to assess cardiovascular autonomic function. These include changes in heart rate during standing up and, Valsalva manoeuvre to assess cardiac parasympathetic activity. **Aim:** To analyse the role of heart rate during standing up and, Valsalva manoeuvre in diagnosing Cardiac Autonomic Neuropathy. **Method:** In this cross sectional study, 30 diabetics were compared with 30 non-diabetics (plasma glucose level between 80-120 mg %) for their autonomic functions. Each subject was evaluated for cardiovascular autonomic neuropathy by heart rate during standing up and, Valsalva manoeuvre. Statistically analysis was performed using t test. **Results:** There was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) association of change in heart rate on standing change in Valsalva Response to diabetic autonomic neuropathy **Conclusion:** Diabetes mellitus is one of the systemic disease which leads to autonomic dysfunctions when compared to non diabetes which may be because of increased duration of disease.

Key words: Diabetes mellitus, Autonomic neuropathy, Autonomic function tests

Introduction

There are currently approximately 40.9 million patients with diabetes mellitus in India and this number is expected to rise to about 69.9 million by the year 2025. [1,2] This high burden of diabetes is likely to be associated with an increase in associated complications. The most common neurological disturbance in diabetes is the involvement of autonomic nervous system. Autonomic nervous system dysfunction is one of the significant complications of diabetes mellitus and this is generally associated with a poor prognosis and negative impact on survival and quality of life in people with diabetes (1,3) From the current study, we attempted to prove that parasympathetic function tests in cases of type II diabetes mellitus by measuring the Valsalva manoeuvre test and Heart rate response to standing and signifying their sensitivity in the early detection for diagnostic purposes(3)

Methodology

This cross sectional study was designed as per the protocol of autonomic function lab, AIIMS, New Delhi. Thirty subjects of Type II diabetes mellitus and thirty non diabetic age matched controls, including both males and females, were assessed for Autonomic functional status after acquiring oral and written consent. The following criteria were followed while selecting the patients as cases:

Inclusion criteria

1. Participants in our study were of two different categories

2. Control subjects who normal subjects (n=30) must be non-diabetic whose plasma glucose concentrations was well within the normal limits 80 to 100 mg%.
3. All control subjects were free of hypertension and other systemic diseases.
4. Control subjects matched for age, sex as that of test group.
5. Diabetes subjects (n=30) who were known patients of diabetes and were under the medical treatment for control of blood sugar. these subjects were diabetic at least for duration of 5 years and more as referred from hospital case paper and were attending the diabetic clinic of S.S.G. hospital medical college Baroda.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Case & controls subjects who did not give consent.
 2. Subjects with hypertensive, suffering from renal failure, suffering from disease that can cause autonomic neuropathy (leprosy, alcoholic neuropathy), neurological, history of tobacco smoking/chewing and alcohol consumption, thoracic skeletal deformities.
- The Autonomic function tests which were performed to assess the cardiovascular parasympathetic functional status:

Heart rate response to standing

Subject was made to lie down in supine posture. ECG electrodes were connected from the subject to the cardiowin system. Subject was asked to relax completely for a minimum period of 10 minutes. Basal heart rate was recorded by using cardiowin system. Subject was asked to stand up immediately and change in heart rate is noted from the monitoring screen of cardiowin. Heart rate response to standing was determined by using the formula heart rate in standing position – heart rate in supine position.

Continuous ECG was recorded from which a 30:15 ratios were calculated. It is the ratio of the longest RR interval around the 30th beat after standing up, to the shortest RR interval around the 15th beat during standing.

On changing the posture from supine to standing heart rate increases immediately by 10-20 beats per minute. (4)

Valsalva manoeuvre

Subject was made to lie down in a semi recumbent or sitting position. Nostrils were closed manually. Mouth piece was put into the mouth of the subject and the Mercury manometer was connected to the mouth piece. ECG machine was switched on for continuous recording. Subject was asked to exhale forcefully into the mercury manometer and asked to maintain the expiratory pressure at 40 mm of Hg for 10 – 15 seconds. ECG changes were recorded throughout the procedure, 30 seconds before and after the procedure. Valsalva ratio was calculated by using the formula.

The Valsalva ratio was calculated as the ratio of the longest RR interval within 20 beats of the manoeuvre, to the shortest RR interval during the manoeuvre. The valsalva ratio is a measure of autonomic parasympathetic functions

Table 1: Distribution of the study population according to different parameters.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Diabetic (n=30)		Non-diabetic (n=30)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1.	Age (years)	58	7	56	7
2.	Height (cm)	162.30	5.04	164.44	6.69

3.	Weight (kg)	59	8	58	4
4.	FBS (mg/dl)	139.93	55.18	92	11
5.	PP ₂ BS (mg/dl)	221.06	68	143	16
6.	Basal Systolic B.P. (mm of Hg)	139.39	23	133	4
7.	Basal diastolic B.P. (mm of Hg)	77.16	8.82	78	9
8.	Basal H.R./min.	84.33	10.5	81	12
9.	Duration of diabetes(years)	8.85	3.05	-	-

Table 2: Distribution of the study according to autonomic function tests.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Diabetic (n=30)		Non-diabetic (n=30)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1..	Heart Rate (/min) response to Standing	1.25*	0.15	1.13	0.12
2.	Valsalva ratio	1.04*	0.16	1.3	0.11

* indicate statistically significant $p < 0.05$

Results

Table 1 shows main anthropometric features which are comparable and well matched in diabetic and control group. The median age of the diabetic group was 58 ± 7 years while control group was 56 ± 7 years, and, mean weight of the diabetic group was 59 ± 8 kg .while control group was 58 ± 4 kg . Similarly mean fasting glucose level were 139.93 ± 55.18 and 92 ± 11 , mean postprandial blood glucose level 221.06 ± 68 and 143 ± 16 in both diabetic and control group respectively. The mean Basal B.P. in and control group and Basal H.R. were 139.69 ± 23 mm Hg and 133 ± 4 mm Hg respectively. . Mean duration of diabetes in diabetic group was 8.85 years.

Table 2 shows. Orthostatic change in heart rate: The mean value of supine heart rate (beats /min) in diabetic and control group and mean value of standing heart arte after 2 minutes (beats/min) in diabetic and control group were 1.25 ± 0.15 , and 1.13 ± 0.12 respectively. There was mean difference was found in heart rate in supine position ($p = 0.12$) and in standing position ($p < 0.05$) but it was not statistically significant

2. Valsalva Response: In our study the mean values of HR response to valsalva ratio in diabetics and control group were 1.04 ± 0.16 vs 1.3 ± 0.1 respectively. The difference of mean values was statistically significant. $p < 0.05$

Discussion

Type 2 diabetes is typically a chronic disease associated with a ten-year-shorter life expectancy. The present study was conducted among the 30 patients with diabetes mellitus reporting to the attending the diabetic clinic of S.S.G. hospital medical college Baroda. The study was conducted with the aim investigate autonomic nervous system involvement in diabetes mellitus by using simple tests.

Diabetes mellitus is one of the high risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Diabetic autonomic neuropathy is a progressive condition in which autonomic nervous system dysfunction is not only more prevalent in diabetics but also worsens as the disease progresses(3) The activity of the autonomic nervous system is of crucial importance in moment to moment regulation of heart rate and blood vessels resistance, thereby controlling arterial pressure, cardiac output and tissue perfusion. (5)

DM patients were compared with the control in our study. This indicates that cardiac autonomic dysfunction is highly associated risk factor in DM patients. (3)

Our study shows difference of mean values of HR response to valsalva ratio in diabetics and control group was statistically significant $p < 0.01$. also showed that Valsalva ratio is lower in diabetic patients than normal persons this reflects decreased parasympathetic function due to decreased vagal tone.

S Sucharita, Ganapathi found that tests of cardiac parasympathetic activity including the heart rate response to standing 30:15 ratio and Valsalva ratio were significantly lower in patients with diabetes compared to the controls ($P < 0.05$) (2)

In my study heart rate response to standing 30:15 ratio in diabetic and control group were 1.25 ± 0.15 , and 1.13 ± 0.12 respectively .and statically significant. Heart rate response to standing up induces reflex tachycardia followed by bradycardia and is both vagal and baroreflex mediated. So in diabetics with autonomic neuropathy there is abnormal response due to damage to the reflex pathways, mediating the response.

The results in our study correlated with the study conducted by ChiranjeeviKumar Endukuru Heart rate response to standing 30:15 Ratio values were decreased in diabetics as compared to controls.

In conclusion, data from the current study demonstrated that diabetics had cardiac parasympathetic nervous system involvement. There was statistically significant association of change in heart rate on standing change in Valsalva Response to diabetic autonomic neuropathy.

The most sensitive parasympathetic cardiac autonomic function test which detects CAN, are heart rate response to standing and heart rate response to Valsalva manoeuvre. (8)

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